

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

INSECT RESISTANCE

Reaction of rice varieties to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

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We evaluated 28 rices for resistance to WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) in the field and in a glasshouse in 1983 kharif. The rices were received through the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project. In the field, WBPH populations were recorded 50 and 60 d after transplanting (DT). Mean population was 3.7 to 19.2/hill at 50 DT and 2.6 to 23.9/hill at 60 DT. Populations declined between 50 and 60 DT on all rices except RP2149-88, RP2147-73, and TN1 (see table).

When evaluated in the seedling bulk test, only eight rices were resistant to WBPH (see table). Cultures with Velutha Cheera as parent were resistant and had low WBPH populations in the field. Cultures with Andrewsali, IET6288, Manoharsali, or Ptb 33 as parents were susceptible.

It is interesting to note that IET6288 and Ptb 33 are resistant to WBPH. IET6288 received resistance from Ptb 21 through CR55-35/IR8. Their high degree of resistance may have been lost in the crossing program. Some rices with susceptible reaction in the seedling bulk test had field resistance to WBPH. The nature of resistance of these rices is being further evaluated. ♪

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Reaction of some promising rice cultures and cultivars to WBPH in the field and in a glasshouse, Pantnagar, India.

Designation	Donor or cross	WBPH (av no./hill)		Damage rating ^a	Reaction ^b
		50 DT	60 DT		
Anaikomban	Donor	4.1	6.8	1.4	R
Eswarmanglam	Donor	5.0	5.9	1.5	R
Mudu Kiriya	Donor	7.7	3.2	2.0	R
Rathu Heenati	Donor	10.4	4.0	2.1	R
MO I	Donor	4.9	6.2	2.2	R
RP2068-17-2-1	Swarndhan/Velutha Cheera	3.7	3.2	2.6	R
RP2068-17-2-2	Swarndhan/Velutha Cheera	4.1	2.8	2.7	R
Ptb33	Donor	6.4	4.4	3.0	R
RP2068-18-4-2	Swarndhan/Velutha Cheera	5.1	4.8	3.6	MR
RP2095-123-1-1	Vikram/Andrewsali	6.2	9.2	5.5	S
RP2095-123-1-5	Vikram/Andrewsali	10.1	4.6	6.1	S
ARC5956	Donor	6.5	4.1	6.8	S
IET7575	Sona/Manoharsali	11.3	9.9	6.8	S
ARC7080	Donor	10.6	7.6	7.4	HS
ARC5984	Donor	3.5	4.5	7.5	HS
Leb Mue Nahng	Donor	6.6	2.6	7.5	HS
IET7948	Ptb 33/TN1	1.2	6.8	7.6	HS
ARC6619	Donor	6.6	7.1	7.9	HS
Andrewsali	Donor	8.1	5.4	7.9	HS
RP2149-109	IET6288/Phalguna	16.4	13.7	8.2	HS
RP2149-71	IET6288/Phalguna	6.2	6.7	8.5	HS
RP2149-73	IET6288/Phalguna	9.3	17.7	8.6	HS
RP2149-88	IET6288/Phalguna	6.8	11.9	8.7	HS
RP2149-58	IET6288/Phalguna	8.1	5.7	8.7	HS
ARC10572 A	Donor	9.3	9.4	8.7	HS
RP2149-96	IET6288/Phalguna	8.7	9.5	9.0	HS
RP2149-86	IET6288/Phalguna	10.0	8.0	9.0	HS
ARC10550	Donor	19.7	17.7	9.0	HS
TN1	—	15.9	23.9	9.0	HS

^a Based on Standard Evaluation System for Rice. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.

Response of different rices to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) populations from different locations in Indonesia

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WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* (Horváth) is widely distributed in Indonesia.

Infestations are generally low, but large populations can cause serious damage.

In 1984 dry season, we collected WBPH from Muara Lawai, South Sumatra; Bulu Kumba, South Sulawesi; Munggu, Bali; and Mataram, Lombok. We

Table 1. Resistance of rice varieties to 5 WBPH populations in the greenhouse, Bogor, Indonesia.

Colony	Resistance ^a on indicated variety				
	TN1	Citanduy	B4032d-Mr-1-3-1	IR36	Colombo
Muara Lawai	8.3	5	3	4	4.3
Bulu Kumba	8.3	3	3	5	2.3
Munggu	7	3	5	5	3.0
Mataram	8.3	4.3	5	5	2.3
Greenhouse	9	3.1	5	—	1.7

^a On scale of 0-9: 0 = no damage, 9 = all plants dead.

Table 2. Weight of honeydew of some WBPH populations, Bogor, Indonesia.

Colony	Honeydew ^a (mg/female)			
	TN1	Citanduy	B4032d-Mr-1-3-1	Colombo
Muara Lawai	7.21 a A	1.09 a B	0.55 a B	1.15 a B
Bulu Kumba	858 a A	0.81 a B	0.49 a B	0.53 a B
Munggu	4.85 a A	1.18 a A	0.52 a A	2.39 a A
Mataram	5.05 a A	2.44 a A	1.12 a A	1.57 a A
Greenhouse	8.74 a A	0.96 a B	0.56 a B	1.67 a B

^a Identical small letters in a column or capital letters in a row indicate no significant difference at the 5% level by DMRT.

Table 3. Population increase of WBPH from different colonies on 1-mo-old rice varieties, Bogor, Indonesia.

Colony	Population increase ^a				
	TN1	Citanduy	B4032d-Mr-1-3-1	IR36	Colombo
Muara Lawai	1217 a C	497 b AB	919 a BC	334 a A	99 ab A
Bulu Kumba	623 a A	174 a A	289 a A	538 a A	144 ab A
Munggu	760 a A	127 a A	355 a A	1084 a A	212 b A
Mataram	904 a C	138 a AB	834 a C	496 a BC	75 a A
Greenhouse	964 a C	352 ab B	788 a B	549 a B	24 a A

^a Identical small letters in a column or capital letters in a row indicate no significant difference at the 5% level by DMRT.

Table 4. Survival of WBPH nymphs on 1-mo-old rice varieties at 10 d after infestation, Bogor, Indonesia.

Colony	Survival ^a (%)				
	TN1	Citanduy	B4032d-Mr-1-3-1	IR36	Colombo
Muara Lawai	78 a C	22 a A	67 a BC	32 a AB	5a A
Bulu Kumba	65 a BC	30 a B	40 a BC	70 a C	2a A
Munggu	52 a BC	13 a AB	47 a BC	67 a C	0a A
Mataram	80 a D	13 a AB	43 a BC	70 a C	0a A
Greenhouse	87 a D	55 a AB	60 a BC	75 a C	3a A

^a Identical small letters in a column or capital letters in a row indicate no significant difference at the 5% level by DMRT.

recorded responses to these populations and one greenhouse population at BORIF of rice varieties Citanduy, B4032d-Mr-1-3-1, IR36, TN1 (susceptible check), and Colombo (resistant check) in seedbox screening tests with three replications (Table 1).

Reaction parameters were honeydew excretion (10 replications), population buildup (3 replications), and survival and development (3 replications). Rices were in a split-plot design with varieties as main plots and insect populations as subplots.

Reaction of rice varieties to different WBPH colonies was uniform. TN1 was susceptible to all colonies, but Citanduy, B4032d-Mr-1-3-1, Colombo, and IR36 were moderately resistant (Table 2). Population increase of colonies differed only slightly on the varieties tested (Table 3). Survival of nymphs also was similar on resistant varieties (Table 4). *J*

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

COLD TOLERANCE

Association of traits governing cold tolerance at early seedling stage in rice

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Degree of yellowing of seedlings and mortality count are measures of cold

tolerance in many countries. In the US, seedling height is the criterion for evaluating cold water tolerance 4 wk after sowing. In Taiwan, cold tolerance is based on the percentage of winter survival. At IRRI, I measured cold hardiness by computing a tolerance

index (TI) based on degree of discoloration and percent survival of the seedlings compared to a resistant check.

I screened 23 parents and their 102 hybrids (17 lines × 6 testers) for cold tolerance at the early seedling stage to evaluate the cultures for relative cold